

NOTES

Azo Complexes : Complexes of Alkali Metal Salts of Some Organic Acids with *o*-Hydroxybenzene-Azo-2-Naphthyl Amine

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AS an extension of our previous work^{1,2} on azo complexes, we are reporting the synthesis of alkali metal salt adducts of *o*-hydroxybenzene-azo-2-naphthylamine (OHBANM), which have two electron releasing groups -OH and -NH₂ in the *o* and *o'* positions to the azo group (-N=N-) and hence would increase the donor property of the azo group. Intramolecular hydrogen bonding in the ligand plays an important role in adduct formation.

Experimental

The ligand OHBANM was prepared by standard method³ (m. p. 192-193°). Solutions of the alkali metal salts used were prepared in 95% ethanol.

The general method of preparation was to add the alkali metal salts of organic acids to hot absolute ethanolic solution of OHBANM in mono molecular ratio. The mixture was refluxed over hot plate using magnetic stirrer for about 1 hr.

The solution, on keeping, yielded crystalline solid adducts. The crystals were filtered, washed with absolute ethanol and dried in an oven at 90°.

Results and Discussion

The adducts are stable when stored under dry condition e.g. in a desiccator, but decompose in the presence of moisture. The adducts are thermally stable. When heated, they undergo decomposition at a temperature higher than the melting point of the ligand suggesting them to be pure compounds. The compounds are sparingly soluble in hot polar solvent. The colour, melting or decomposition temperatures and analytical data of the compounds are given in Table 1.

The presence of electron releasing -OH and -NH₂ groups at *o* and *o'* positions to the azo group increases the coordinating capacity of the azo-nitrogen which perhaps takes part in association. The NH₂, O-H and -N=N- frequencies of ligand and adducts are listed in Table 2.

In ligand OHBANM, we observe that the two N-H stretch vibrations appear as medium peaks at ~ 3325 cm⁻¹ and ~ 3260 cm⁻¹. In the alkali metal adducts, the ~ 3325 cm⁻¹ band remains unaffected after association, but the ~ 3260 cm⁻¹ band shifts down to ~ 3125 cm⁻¹. It suggests that there has been decrease in the bond order of N-H. The OH group in the ligand is hydrogen bonded and does not show up at the original place. In OHBANM adducts with alkali metal salts, the O-H

TABLE 1

Compound	Colour	Melting/decomp. (d) temp. (°C)	Found (%)				Calcd. (%)			
			C	H	N	M	C	H	N	M
OHBANM=L	Deep violet	193	72.98	4.89	16.01	—	73.00	4.94	15.99	—
Na1N2N.L	Brown	209(d)	68.10	4.45	12.57	4.92	68.11	4.13	12.23	5.02
K1N2N.L	Brown	213	65.65	4.22	11.99	8.11	65.82	4.01	11.81	8.22
Li8HQ.L	Deep green	237	72.25	4.79	13.34	—	72.46	4.58	13.52	1.69
Na8HQ.L	Deep green	232	69.45	4.62	13.34	5.11	69.74	4.41	13.02	5.34
K8HQ.L	Brown	245	67.11	4.47	12.87	8.34	67.26	4.26	12.55	8.74
NaONP.L	Deep green	225	62.11	4.24	13.51	5.12	62.26	4.01	13.20	5.42
KONP.L	Deep green	228	59.89	4.01	12.93	8.95	60.00	3.86	12.72	8.86
Na2H3NA.L	Red	242	68.12	4.41	9.11	4.21	68.49	4.22	8.87	4.86
K2H3NA.L	Red	246	66.14	4.21	8.96	7.42	66.25	4.08	8.58	7.97
Na.anth.L	Deep green	225	65.12	4.71	13.57	5.12	65.40	4.50	13.27	5.54
K.anth.L	Bright red	215	63.44	4.36	12.87	8.46	63.01	4.33	12.78	8.70
NaSalA.L	Deep green	233	65.43	4.44	10.21	5.12	65.24	4.25	9.92	5.43
KSaI.A.L	Brown	227	62.42	4.32	10.11	8.23	62.87	4.10	9.56	8.88
NaSaI.H.L	Deep red	226	67.51	4.72	10.72	5.12	67.81	4.42	10.31	5.65
Na.acac.L	Royal blue	—								

(Soluble in ethanol)

1N2N=1-nitroso-2-naphthol; 8HQ=8-hydroxyquinoline; ONP=*o*-nitrophenol; 2H3NA=2-hydroxy-3-naphthoic acid; anth=anthranilic acid; SaIa=Salicylic acid; SaIH=Salicylaldehyde; acac=acetylacetone.

TABLE 2

Compound	N-H frequencies (cm^{-1})	O-H frequencies (cm^{-1})	-N=N- frequencies (cm^{-1})
OHBANM=L	3325 3260		1585
NaIN ₂ N.L	3325 3125	2450 1960	1525
KIN ₂ N.L	3325 3150-25	2450 1920	1505
NaONP.L	3325 3125	2400 1940	1510
KONP.L	3325 3115	2400 1860	1507
Na ₂ H ₃ N ₄ .L	3300 3225	2400 1880	1530
K ₂ H ₃ N ₄ .L	3325 3125	2400 1880	1530
Na ₈ HQ.L	3350(br)		1505
Na ₈ AlH.L		2380 1860	1500
K ₈ Al ₄ .L		2380 1860	1505

br = broad.

frequencies show up as one or two broad humps, one at $\sim 2500 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and the other at $1800\text{-}1960 \text{ cm}^{-1}$. It suggests strong association of the OH group.

The -N=N- stretching frequency at 1535 cm^{-1} in the ligand has been spotted between 1525 cm^{-1} to 1500 cm^{-1} in the adducts, suggesting again the association of -N=N- group in the alkali metal adducts.

Our present work also shows that strong intramolecular hydrogen bonding existing in the ligand breaks on complexation. It has been further observed that ligands, which have stronger intramolecular hydrogen bonding, form stable alkali metal adducts.

References

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Interaction Products of Triphenylphosphine Oxide with Some Organotin Halides

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COMPLEXES of triorganophosphine oxide with a variety of metal salts have been extensively studied¹⁻³. Syntheses and characterisation of adducts of the Lewis base with organometallic moieties have also been reported⁴⁻¹⁶. Molecular

addition compounds of triphenylphosphine oxide (TPPO) with organotin moieties appear not to have received adequate attention. In continuation of our studies on organotins¹⁷⁻²¹, we report here the interaction of TPPO with some organotins which yielded molecular addition compounds of the type $R_n\text{SnX}_{4-n}\cdot\text{L}$ (R=phenyl or butyl; X=Cl or Br, n=1,2 or 3 and L=TPPO). The compounds have been characterised by elemental analysis, melting point and their data on conductance, molecular weight, ir and mass spectrometry have been discussed.

Experimental

Di or triorganotin halides were prepared according to literature methods²². TPPO (Carlsile) and other reagents of analytical grade (B.D.H./S. Merck) were used without further purification.

In a typical reaction, 2 m mole of an organotin derivative and equimolar amount of TPPO were refluxed in 40 ml of benzene/chloroform for about 1 hr. A suitable volume of pet. ether (60-80)/ether was added to this (in some cases reaction mixture was kept in a fridge) and the solid so obtained was separated, washed with pet. ether, recrystallised from benzene-pet. ether solvent pair and dried under vacuum. The yield was about 66%.

The m. ps. of the adducts were determined on electrically operated apparatus (M/s. Toshniwal Bros., Bombay). Elemental analyses were done by micro analytical method but tin was estimated as stannic acid. The metal was weighed as oxide after ignition.

The infrared spectra of TPPO and their adducts with organotins were recorded in the region 4000-200 using Perkin Elmer IR spectrophotometer, model 521. Calibration was performed with a polystyrene film.

Conductance was measured in benzene by Phillips, type PR 9500, conductivity bridge using dip type conductivity cell having a cell constant 0.7584. The molecular weights of the adducts were determined cryoscopically in benzene. Mass spectrometer, Hitachi model No. RMU-6E, was used for obtaining mass spectra.

Results and Discussion

Experimental data of the adducts are given in Table 1. The adducts melt in the range of $62\text{-}175^\circ$ while $\text{Ph-SnCl}_3\cdot\text{TPPO}$ do not melt up to 250° . They are soluble in common organic solvents, are thermally stable and do not decompose when heated to their m. ps. for several hr. They are insensitive to atmospheric moisture but easily hydrolyse when refluxed with water or aqueous ammonia yielding polymeric organotin oxide as the final product. The conductance values in $10^{-3}M$ solutions indicate

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